

Underwater breadcrumb localization

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Abstract—In most cases, underwater localization implies a fusion of two or more sensors, usually inertial and acoustic ones. Acoustic localization demands the deployment of the acoustic baseline if precise measurement is needed. Using a fixed pre-deployed baseline limits the accuracy of location estimates outside certain operating areas defined by the baseline. In case an AUV or a diver has to be localized underwater, their trajectory is usually unknown, so it is a challenging task to deploy a baseline in such a manner that localization is accurate. In this paper, the sequential deployment of acoustic breadcrumb modems is suggested as the alternative to the conventional baseline deployment. This type of sequentially deployed acoustic baseline in combination with IMU is first simulated and later on tested in a constrained environment in shallow waters in order to show what are the main challenges, advantages and potential problems with this type of localization.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the underwater environment, precise localization is still a big challenge. As GPS does not work underwater due to the high attenuation of electromagnetic waves in the water, the most common methods for underwater localization are based on dead reckoning and acoustic localization. Despite the fact that using dead reckoning as a localization technique is quite simple, it suffers from some problems if it's used for a longer time or distance, e.g. position drift caused by IMU sensors, especially the cheaper ones [1]. On the other hand, acoustic localization also has its pros and cons that differ on the type of acoustic localization. If the localization method measures a single-range between the anchor node with the known location and the target (diver, AUV, or some other object of interest), that kind of localization technique is called single-range localization which is well-known for its observability problem [2], [3]. An additional acoustic node will be needed if the TDOA (Time Difference Of Arrival) method is used for localization. Anyhow, radial unboundedness and sensitivity to the noise reduce the usability of the procedure, especially for far sources [4]. Using three or more acoustical anchors that form a baseline (LBL, SBL, or USBL) usually provides the

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most precise localization of the underwater target. In most cases, they rely on a triangulation algorithm [5]. The flaws of these localization methods are usually high prices of the localization systems due to precise clocks that keep all of the anchors in sync. A common problem that is worth mentioning regarding all of the acoustic localization techniques mentioned above is multi-path, especially in shallow waters. Although there are other proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors and localization techniques that are making accurate measurements (such as sonar, DVL, and USBL), they are quite expensive and therefore will be used in this paper only as sensors that provide ground-truth information about the location of the AUV.

In this paper, we introduce a new underwater localization technique - underwater breadcrumb localization. Similarly to some already researched localization techniques based on Kalman filter and sensor fusion [6], the breadcrumb localization exploits measurements from IMU and acoustic ranging to get the position estimate of the AUV. The most accent is given to the sequential deployment of acoustic breadcrumbs during the mission. This type of acoustic baseline deployment is rare but can be seen in the paper [7], but with a much different localization technique. Our proposed fusion of inertial sensors and sequentially deployed acoustic baseline could highly improve the accuracy of the AUVs or divers in shallow environments which has been the main motivation for implementing this type of sensor fusion.

II. MOTIVATION

For communication and localization during experiments in a real environment, we use Nanomodem V3 acoustic modems [8]. Nanomodems are low-cost acoustic modems capable of sending messages up to 64 bytes in length. Nanomodems can also measure a range between each other. Their operating range is around 2 km. During the trials on island Pag in Croatia, after outlier rejection (mostly due to multipath), the standard deviation of the range measurements was less than 10 centimeters in the operating range under 500 meters in shallow waters which we have found quite satisfying (laguna Poveljana on island Pag, depth: 5-10 meters).

As it is common to have IMU on all of ASVs, ROVs and AUVs, we decided to use IMU as a primary sensor for the extended Kalman filter (EKF). Afterward, due to the measured precision and affordability of the Nanomodems, we got to the idea to use them as the breadcrumbs during missions.

Figure 1: Visual representation of the breadcrumb algorithm

III. ALGORITHM

As the target moves, IMU measurement error accumulates and the covariance estimate of the filter diverges as time passes by. In order to bound that error, range measurements between breadcrumbs and the target, which is in our case AUV, are then used as additional measurements in the EKF. The observation matrix that is dependent on and the rest of the filter is expanded accordingly. With this sensor fusion, observability is ensured with IMU measurements and we bound the IMU drift using the single-range measurement between the breadcrumb and the target. Although the IMU estimate drifts as time passes, it doesn't drift much between two range measurements that have a much smaller sample rate than measurements from the IMU. That can be helpful when it comes to the outlier rejection of the range measurements. Those outliers are mainly caused by the multipath and tend to be easily detected if we have a position estimate based on IMU data in the meantime between two ranges. If many outliers are detected among range measurements, or the AUV's trajectory is similar to the trajectories that are not observable in a single-range scenario [9], AUV deploys a new breadcrumb and ensures better position estimation in further steps. In the same manner, the algorithm repeats and breadcrumbs are being deployed one after the other, sequentially, when needed as shown in figure 1.

IV. SIMULATION

The first step taken towards the experiment in the real environment was a MATLAB simulation. The simulation was in 2D and the depth of the AUV was neglected. Input measurements for the designed EKF were artificial data from IMU and Nanomodem sensor. After the EKF estimated the position of the AUV, results were compared with dead reckoning and ground truth. In order to show how the position of the breadcrumb affects the quality of the position estimate, another simulation was done, but this time, with a different location of the breadcrumb. Results are presented in figure 2. It can be seen that the position of the breadcrumb greatly affected

the quality of the position estimate. In the figure 3 simulation results are presented after more than one breadcrumb is used for localization and measurement noise is added. The positions of the breadcrumbs are chosen in a manner that they are always on or near the AUV's path. The main reason for that is the fact that this localization method could be used among divers that sequentially drop the breadcrumbs along the path during the mission. According to [10], the acoustic baseline should be always deployed in a such shape that acoustic links between the modems are not co-linear in space. That deployment condition was respected during the simulation as can be seen at 3.

Figure 2: Comparison of the position estimates with different breadcrumb positions

V. TRIAL DATA COLLECTION AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

After the simulation, the algorithm was tested with ASV aPad shown in figure 4. ASV was driven in a lawn-mower pattern in the Olympic-sized sea pool Ilirija at Biograd an Moru, Croatia, visible at figure 4. At the sea bed inside of the pool, there were five Nanomodems - breadcrumbs, that were continuously ranged. Although ASV floats and does not

Figure 3: Simulation results with more breadcrumbs and added measurement noise

experience noticeable heave, a 3D model was used in EKF in order to minimize the position estimate error. Trajectory of the ASV and

A. Estimating the locations of the breadcrumbs

If acoustic ranging data wants to be used for precise underwater localization, it is important to have highly accurate positions of the breadcrumbs after they are deployed. During the trials in Biograd na Moru, the breadcrumbs' locations were estimated using the ASV aPad's GPS and range measurements from aPad to breadcrumbs. The ASV was driving in a lawn-mower pattern while its GPS position, IMU data and ranging data, and downward-looking camera footage were recorded. The idea behind this was to compare the GPS position of the breadcrumb estimated from camera footage with the location estimated with GPS and ranging data using a spherical trilateration algorithm.

1) *Estimation using camera:* The ASV approached the breadcrumb from the surface and filmed it for 10 seconds while keeping the breadcrumb in the middle of the frame for the best accuracy possible. After the breadcrumb was filmed, the GPS position of the ASV aPad during these 10 seconds was averaged, resulting in the breadcrumb GPS location estimate, which will be later used as ground truth.

2) *Estimation using GPS and ranging data - spherical trilateration:* All of the gathered GPS and ranging data is shown in figure 6 where intersections of range measurements,

Figure 4: ASV aPad used in the experiment Olympic-sized sea pool Ilirija and lawn-mower trajectory of the ASV aPad

Figure 5: Camera footage of the breadcrumb placed on the seabed (white object in the middle of the picture)

centered at GPS locations of the ASV aPad, show the most probable area where the breadcrumb is located. This intersection is also the place where the spherical trilateration algorithm will converge.

	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	Overall
Failed requests	21%	42%	42%	40%	38%	37%
Successful ranging	79%	58%	58%	60%	62%	63%

Table I: Success and failure rate of ranging for breadcrumbs B1 to B5

3) *Comparison of the estimates*: If locations gathered by the camera (ground truth) and trilateration are compared (visible at figure 6), there is an average error of 4.00 meters in the North-East plane for five of the breadcrumbs. This error is that big because there is still some multipath that passed through the Nanomodem undetected - most probably surface reflection that is usually hard to detect. Therefore, in the future, there must be a range filter that will discard all of the ranges based on velocity estimated from inertial sensors - if the range difference between two timestamps is bigger than the estimated velocity multiplied by the time difference, range measurement is discarded.

B. Data fusion - used methods and problems

1) *Estimation using IMU*: Collected IMU data during trials has caused the most problems and filtering that data didn't produce any satisfying results. Implementing extended Kalman filter also did not result in any improvements regarding localization estimate.

2) *Multipath*: As the data recorded was intentionally recorded inside the sea pool, a lot of multipath was expected. Used acoustic modem for breadcrumbs, Nanomodem V3, is using spread spectrum technique to combat the multipath problem [8]. As it can range in open waters more than 2 km, ranging in the pool regarding the distance between two modems should not be a problem, so all of the dropped range requests are linked to the multipath. The number of ranging requests from aPad to breadcrumbs is tracked and their success and failure rate is shown in the table I. When the results are visualized (figure 7), it can be seen there is no easily-noticeable pattern of the locations where the requests fail for breadcrumbs B3 and B1.

Anyhow, if all of the requests are put into the same graph some patterns occur. It can be seen that the furthest locations and locations near the pool walls tend to fail in ranging. Also, some periodic patterns of successful ranging requests are visible in the upper left corner of figure 8.

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The expected outcome of this experiment is the confirmation of the breadcrumb localization and implementation of the algorithm for the position estimation of the AUV that can move in all of the six degrees of freedom. Unfortunately, collected trial data from the IMU sensor wasn't eventually used for estimating the location of the AUV or the diver in shallow underwater environments. Ranging data gave much more promising results, but still, it has to be filtered with a velocity filter that will remove all of the sudden jumps in range caused by multipath. Both the extended Kalman

Figure 6: Visualisation of ranging data and breadcrumb location estimates calculated with camera(with GPS fix) and spherical trilateration algorithm for breadcrumbs B2 and B3 respectively

filter and range velocity filter rely on IMU data which significantly influences the quality of location estimate. From the preliminary results, we can conclude that there is potential in fusing the inertial and sequentially deployed acoustic sensors, but major changes have to be done on the side of the IMU sensor that didn't produce satisfactory measurements. After that barrier is crossed, the implementation of an

Figure 7: Visualisation of successful and failed range requests for breadcrumbs B3 and B1 respectively

Figure 8: Success and failure rate of ranging for all of the breadcrumbs

extended Kalman filter can be done.

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